

Change in People's Attitude towards Dental Esthetic

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Abstract:-

Introduction: Esthetic is branch of philosophy that deals with nature of beauty. Esthetics makes us happy and confident. Most of the people are concerned with improving their social acceptance and appearance than they are with improving their oral function or health.

Aim: ¹To determine the level of dental awareness, attitude, satisfaction regarding dental esthetic among people.

Methods: The study was questionnaire based which contained a set of 15 multiple choice of questions. This questionnaire was mainly used to identify people's ¹level of awareness, satisfaction and attitude towards dental esthetics.

Result: The ⁴total of 302 potential participants were emailed & invited to respond to the questionnaire. Most of the participants were from various degree colleges. Among those surveyed 71.2% we're satisfied with dental treatment & 77.8% people consulted to dentist regarding the dental problems. Most undergone treatment among the people was orthodontic treatment (braces). Then majority of participants that is (94.7%) responded that there is change in people's attitude towards dental esthetic.

Conclusion: Through this questionnaire study conducted among 302 peoples ¹we concluded that more than three fourth of people's satisfied with their dental treatment and aware about the dental esthetics.

Keywords:- Dental esthetic, dental satisfaction, dental awareness, dental appearance, people's attitude

I. INTRODUCTION

Esthetic is branch of philosophy that deals with nature of beauty. Esthetics makes us happy and confident. On an emotional level it provides feeling of happiness and calm. It connect us to our ability to reflect on & appreciate the world around us which gives us feelings of satisfaction and hope. Esthetic play a very important role because it is a measure reason to feel pleasant and confident[. Every person wants to look attractive and beautiful. Esthetics defines through external appearance including facial appearance, attractive smile, body posture. In facial appearance Smile is our most valuable tool to look beautiful & confident. Smiling helps you to communicate and improves bond with each other. Beautiful Smile attracts a person immediately & it has

potential to boost individuals mood and feels refreshing. A confident smile increases individuals self esteem. Physical attractiveness is specially trend now a days among society. It also helps to strengthen the relationship among people. A pleasing and attractive smile enhances the impression of a person in a society. ¹ancient times as many have tried to accomplish and maintain it¹

In modern era, young people are very aware and concerned about their appearance particularly facial appearance. In this , social media is highly influencing factor to change the people's attitude towards esthetic. Gender, age, education level are the socio demographic factors which has impact on dental esthetic. Female are more sensitive than male regarding the facial appearance. Compare to older individuals younger individuals are more conscious about their esthetics. One of the reason of increase in popularity of esthetics is the positive attitude towards it. Thus, esthetic is a tool to improve a one's appearance ²

Dental Esthetic enhance the overall appearance of the teeth. Now a days esthetic consideration is the reason to request dental treatment, every people wants to look attractive and beautiful. The main objective of dental esthetic is to keep the teeth aligned and improve its structure, colour, shape. Dental esthetic is both restorative and preventive measure. ¹Discrepancy between dentist and patient's perception for esthetic needs, which in some cases result in esthetic appearance lower than patients expectation has been found so attitude of patients towards dental esthetic and preferences should be recognized ²in order to reach the expectation of the patient.³

Most common factors which affects dental esthetics are malocclusion(crowding, spacing, incompetent lips) ,caries,poor oral hygiene,oral habits.Malocclusion is primary factor which affects dental esthetics among yonger individuals.Many social media platforms influences awareness about dental esthetics treatment such as teeth whitening, bridges, orthodontic treatment, implant. Desire for good look also seems to be increase in various jobs / fields like lecturers , actors,etc.⁴

There are various perceptions among people that dental esthetic in children and adults is associated with intelligence. Poor dental esthetic/smile are considered as the inferior intelligence while the ideal smile are considered as superior to it specially in adults. These people have more chance to find the job. ²It has also shown that esthetic

restoration treatment has positive effect on patients self esteem and satisfaction and ²on their daily living and quality of life therefore it is vital importance for dentist to be able to define what exactly patient require and what actually he /she needs related to esthetic treatment. Not only adults, but also parents of children are conscious about dental esthetic. ¹The beauty of the teeth doesn't only extend towards appearance of teeth but also include oral health . ⁵

²Recognizing the perception of patient's and their satisfaction with the present dental appearance and desire treatment to improve dental esthetic can guide clinician to strategize to improve esthetic. ⁶

This study aimed to examine change in people's attitude towards dental esthetics. Feedback from various degree colleges students to evaluate awareness among the dental esthetics.

II. METHODOLOGY

A cross section survey was done to determine the attitude of people towards dental esthetics among general population. A questionnaire of 15 questions was formulated and uploaded in google form. The questionnaire was randomly circulated in various students of degree colleges (BA, Bcom, Bsc, Medical, Dental, Physiotherapy) ⁵who were willing to participate in this study and honestly answer all the questions.The questions was simple,easy and where in english language.The students who didn't ⁹respond to the questions appropriately were excluded from study.The researchers distributed the questionnaire to the various degree colleges students by using google document forms ⁵and requested them to read the questions carefully and answer all the questions accurately & honestly.The collected data were confidential.Descriptive analysis was done to find out the frequency distribution of the relation between people's attitude towards dental esthetic appearance. Pie chart and graph of same were obtained and analysed.

A. Ethical Approval

The Institutional Ethics Committee of the ³Maharashtra Institute of Dental Science and Research, Latur under Registration No. MIDSRS/STU/IEC-111/837/2022 approved the study.

B. Informed Consent:

⁴The participants were informed that their participation in the study's questionnaire was entirely on a voluntary basis before they responded. The formal informed consent was waived by the Institutional Ethics Committee.

III. RESULTS

The ⁴total of 302 potential participants were emailed & invited to respond to the questionnaire. Most of the participants were from various degree Colleges.

(Table 1 and Graph). Out of 302 participants, 176(58.3%) female and 126(41.7%) male students ¹⁰participated in this study. The majority of the participants were female.

Pie Chart 1: Distribution of people according to gender.

Pie Chart 2: Shows that Did it helped participants to improve their esthetics. In which 76.2% participants responded yes, 4.8% responded no and 19% participants has no review

Graph 1: Shows that what are the other causes that affect dental esthetic then 144 (47.7%) participant responded fluorinated water , 98(32.5%) participant responded not maintaining proper oral hygiene , 53(17.5%) participant responded habits like tobacco and betel nut/smoking, 78(25.8%) participant are not know about any cause that affect dental esthetic

Graph 2: Shows that shows that what are the factors that play important role in esthetics then 267(88.4%) participant responded smile , 86(28.5%) participant responded facial form , 49(16.2%) participant responded lips , 46(15.2%) participant responded nose , 34 (11.3%) participant responded eyebrows , 21(7%) participant responded others.

Question	Total responses	Yes	No	None
Q.If yes, what was the reason for the visit -Spacing/ malaligned teeth -caries -Missing teeth -Discolored teeth -None	302	235 77.8%	67 22.2%	
Q.If yes then select from the following -Pain -Sensitivity -Dislodgement -Irritation -None	302	133 44.4%	93 30.8%	75 24.8%
Q.What is your opinion regarding cost/expenses about esthetic dental treatment -Costly -Affordable -Not affordable	294	224 76.2%	14 4.8%	56 19%
Q.If yes then select from the following -Neem stick -Brush with baking soda -Brush with lemon juice -Tooth whitening ko powder/lotion None	302	232 76.8%	70 23.2%	
Q.According to you, what other factors play important role in esthetics -Smile -Facial form -Lips -Nose -Eyebrows -Others	302	286 94.7%	16 5.3%	
Q .Do you think that social media has any impact on esthetic awareness -Yes -No	302	280 92.7%	22 7.3%	
Q.Are you aware about recent advances in esthetic dentistry -Yes -No	297	248 83.5%	49 16.5%	

Table 1: Percentage analysis of "yes or no and none" responses to questions of "Change in people's attitude towards esthetics"

Question 3 (Reason for the visit)	Responses with percentages
Spacing / misaligned teeth	141 46.7%
Caries	54 17.9%
Missing teeth	22 7.3%
Discoloured teeth	30 9.9%
None	64 21.2%

Table 2: Percentage analysis of reasons for the visit to dental clinics

Question no 4 (Treatment undergone)	Responses with percentages
Orthodontic treatment	135 44.7%
Tooth coloured restoration	61 20.2%
Bridge/implant	21 7%
Whitening of teeth	32 10.6%
None	70 23.2%

Table 3: Percentage analysis of treatment undergone by patients regarding the problem.

IV. DISCUSSION

As per our knowledge, this study was an attempt to examine people's attitude towards dental esthetics. The main outcome of the study was that people are more aware about dental esthetics. Most of the participants reported that esthetics play important role in their daily routine life.

Majority of participants thinks that smile plays important role in dental esthetics and participants responded that social media has great impact on esthetics awareness and they are also aware about recent advances.

V. CONCLUSION

Through this questionnaire we concluded that more than three fourth of people's satisfied with their dental treatment and aware about the dental esthetics and dental esthetic has greater impact on psychological status .

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